

SYSTEMATIC REVIEW: DYNAMICS OF POSTPARTUM MENTAL HEALTH: RISK FACTORS, INTERVENTIONS, AND THE ROLE OF SOCIAL SUPPORT

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Abstract

Postpartum mental health is an important issue that affects the well-being of mothers and children. Mental health disorders such as depression and anxiety are at high risk for mothers after giving birth. Risk factors, interventions, and social support play an important role in the dynamics of postpartum maternal mental health. This study aims to evaluate the factors that influence postpartum mental health as well as interventions that can be applied to overcome this problem. This research used a systematic review that examined 42 journals related to postpartum mental health. A literature search was conducted via PubMed and Google Scholar with relevant keywords such as postpartum mental health, risk factors, interventions, and social support. Studies that met inclusion criteria were analyzed to evaluate risk factors, interventions, and the role of social support in maternal mental health after childbirth. The results of the review show that the main risk factors for postpartum mental health disorders include hormonal changes, history of mental disorders, psychosocial stress, and lack of social support. Effective interventions include cognitive and behavioral therapy, psychosocial support, as well as holistic approaches such as yoga. Social support from partners, family and community has been proven to improve maternal emotional well-being and reduce stress. Postpartum mental health dynamics are influenced by risk factors that can be managed with appropriate interventions and social support. This research suggests a multidisciplinary approach to support postpartum maternal mental health, and further research is needed to evaluate the long-term effectiveness of such interventions.

Keyword: Mental Health, Postpartum, Risk Factors, Intervension, Social Support.

1. INTRODUCTION

Postpartum mental health is a crucial aspect of maternal well-being and child development. The postpartum period is characterized by significant hormonal, physical, and psychological changes, which can increase the risk of mental disorders such as postpartum depression. According to WHO data, around 13% of women who have just given birth experience mental health problems, especially depression [1,2].

Various risk factors have been identified as contributing to the emergence of postpartum mental disorders. These factors include a history of previous psychiatric disorders, anxiety during pregnancy, lack of social support, poor marital relationships, and stressful life events. In addition, complications during pregnancy or childbirth, such as emergency caesarean section or premature birth, can also increase the risk of postpartum [3,4,5].

Interventions to address postpartum mental health problems focus on early detection and appropriate treatment. Common approaches include psychological counseling, cognitive behavioral therapy, and, in some cases, the use of antidepressant medications. Studies show that social support, especially from a partner, has an important role in preventing and reducing symptoms of postpartum depression. Emotional and practical support from her husband can help mothers adjust to their new role and reduce the stress they experience [6].

Social support does not only come from your partner, but also from family, friends and community. Research shows that mothers who receive adequate social support tend to have better mental health status after giving birth. Conversely, a lack of social support can increase the

risk of postpartum depression. Therefore, it is important to increase awareness of the importance of social support for new mothers as part of prevention and intervention strategies [7].

Given the complexity of risk factors and the importance of appropriate interventions, this study aimed to conduct a systematic review of postpartum mental health dynamics. The main focus is identifying risk factors, evaluating the effectiveness of various interventions, and understanding the role of social support in supporting maternal mental health after childbirth. It is hoped that the results of this research will provide comprehensive insight for the development of more effective prevention and treatment strategies [8].

2. METHODOLOGY

The PICO (Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome) methodological approach in this systematic review study optimizes a systematic and structured evaluation of postpartum mental health dynamics, highlighting risk factors, interventions, and the role of social support. A literature search was carried out through the PubMed and Google Scholar databases using relevant keywords (Postpartum Mental Health OR Postpartum Depression AND Risk Factors OR Intervention AND Social Support). The search process was carried out systematically and in stages, starting from identifying relevant studies, selecting studies based on predetermined criteria, to data extraction and analysis of results..

The research results are then presented in the form of a PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) diagram to provide a clear, systematic and transparent picture of the study selection process and presentation of research results.

Systematically, a search was carried out through the PubMed, Scopus and Google Scholar databases with keywords related to postpartum mental health, namely "Dynamics of Postpartum Mental Health", resulting in 6340 initial journals. After removing duplicates, 5736 journals

remained which were further filtered based on abstracts and full text to 305 journals. Furthermore, it is adjusted based on inclusion criteria including peer-reviewed journals in the last 10 years (2014-2024) that discuss risk factors, interventions, or social support in postpartum mental health, with clear quantitative or qualitative methods. Meanwhile, exclusion criteria include irrelevant articles, opinions without research data, and inappropriate populations. After final selection, 216 journals met the inclusion criteria, consisting of 14 journals about risk factors, 14 journals about interventions, and 14 journals about the role of social support, which were then analyzed to understand the dynamics of postpartum mental health as well as effective prevention and intervention strategies.

3. RESULT

The results of this systematic review show that of the 42 pieces of literature that meet the inclusion criteria, each risk factor, intervention, and social support play an important role in the dynamics of postpartum mental health. Factors such as hormonal changes, psychosocial stress, and lack of social support increase the risk of mental disorders, while interventions such as psychological counseling, cognitive therapy, and emotional support from partners and family have proven effective in helping mothers adapt after giving birth. postpartum and reduces symptoms of mental disorders. However, this study has limitations, such as variations in methods and duration of intervention as well as differences in population characteristics. Therefore, further research is needed to confirm the results and evaluate the long-term effectiveness of the intervention.

3.1 Postpartum Mental Health Risk Factors

From the 14 pieces of literature analyzed, several main factors were found that contributed to postpartum mental health disorders. First, fluctuations in the hormones estrogen and progesterone after giving birth can affect the brain's neurochemical balance, increasing the risk of depression and anxiety. Second, mothers with a previous history of mental disorders, such as depression or anxiety, are more susceptible to postpartum depression. Third, psychosocial pressure caused by changes in the role of mother, workload, and lack of emotional and financial readiness can trigger mental disorders. Fourth, lack of social support from a partner, family, or social environment can increase the risk of social isolation and emotional stress. Lastly, birth complications such as premature birth or a baby with certain health problems, as well as a traumatic birth experience, can trigger postpartum anxiety and depression.

3.2 Postpartum mental Health Interventions

The 14 pieces of literature analyzed show that various forms of intervention have been carried out to help postpartum mothers overcome mental health disorders, including: Cognitive and Behavioral Therapy (CBT): This method has been proven to be effective in managing symptoms of postpartum depression and anxiety by helping mothers change their thinking patterns. negative and improve coping mechanisms. Psychosocial Support: Maternal support groups, community-based therapy, and emotional counseling can improve mothers' psychological well-being by providing a space for sharing experiences and practical solutions. Pharmacological Interventions: The use of antidepressants and anxiolytics, although effective, is still a matter of debate, especially in terms of safety for breastfeeding mothers. Holistic Approach: Several studies show that yoga, meditation, and music therapy can help reduce stress and improve a mother's mental well-being postpartum. Parenting Education and Training: Programs that help mothers understand parenting and stress management are proven to increase self-confidence and reduce anxiety.

3.3 The Role of Social Support in Postpartum Mental Health

The 14 pieces of literature analyzed consistently show that social support has a crucial role in maintaining maternal mental health after giving birth. Some forms of support that have been shown to be beneficial include: Spousal Support: The husband's active involvement in caring for the baby and sharing household tasks has been shown to reduce stress levels and increase the mother's emotional satisfaction. Family Support: The presence of family, especially the biological

mother or in-laws, in helping care for the baby can reduce feelings of overwhelm and provide emotional calm for the mother. Professional Support: Health workers such as midwives, doctors and psychologists who provide education and mental health monitoring can help with early detection and prevention of psychological disorders. Social Support from the Community: New mothers' groups, either in person or through social media, provide a sense of community and reduce the risk of social isolation.

4. CONCLUSION

A systematic review of 42 journals shows that postpartum mental health is influenced by various risk factors, but can be managed with appropriate interventions and adequate social support. Therefore, a multidisciplinary approach involving health workers, families and communities is very necessary to prevent and treat mental health disorders in postpartum mothers. For further research, studies with more controlled designs are needed to evaluate the long-term effectiveness of various interventions and develop more appropriate strategies to support maternal mental health after giving birth.

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